

Intermittent Remote Visual Servoing in a Heterogeneous Robotic Team

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Abstract—Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) are becoming common technology used for various purposes. Most of the applications constitute monitoring and surveillance. In addition to being passive actors in search and rescue missions, UAVs take on more active roles in the form of aerial manipulators capable of physical interaction with the environment. In this paper, we present the collaborative approach between UAV and robot manipulator, where the robot manipulator plays the role of the visual observer. We also present a UAV control based on visual servoing, a state machine for suction-based object grasping in a GNSS-denied scenario, and study the effect of different message drop probabilities on the system performance. The presented scenario is one of the tasks of the MBZIRC competition. Results are presented in the official contest simulator, Ignition Gazebo.

Index Terms—visual servoing; aerial manipulator; visual observer; ROS 2;

I. INTRODUCTION

Maritime security is one of the key international issues that could benefit from new systems for autonomous operations. Today, maritime security is threatened by terrorist activities, illegal immigration, and piracy. In addition to combating these threats, autonomous systems such as unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) could also be used to enforce International Maritime Organization (IMO) regulations. For example, the IMO 2020 regulation aims to reduce sulfur oxide emissions from ships to protect the environment and human health [1]. In the Strait of Gibraltar, autonomous UAVs are already operating beyond visual line of sight to monitor levels of these gasses and alert authorities to conduct detailed inspections [2]. Unmanned aerial vehicles have been used extensively for monitoring, photography, surveillance, inspection, parcel delivery, construction, image and video mapping, search and rescue, and military applications [3]. Most unmanned aerial systems today rely on the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) for localization and positioning. The nominal reported accuracy of commercial grade GNSS systems ranges from 5 to 15 m, while differential GNSS accuracy ranges from 0.5 to 3 m [4]. For accurate position estimation, real-time kinematic GNSS is used. However, such a system is expensive to install and maintain, especially on the vessels. Apart from the GNSS-denied environments, visual servoing can be especially useful for tasks like precision multirotor landing on the vessel where GNSS is not accurate enough for the environmental conditions present [5], [6]. Therefore, it is reasonable to explore ways to control aerial systems in GNSS-denied environments.

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Fig. 1: Ignition Gazebo simulation environment of the MBZIRC challenge as an experimental testbed for object retrieval.

Since the early days, robotic challenges and competitions have been used as means to research and develop advanced robotic systems and spur innovation. The most notable challenges organized to tackle some of the hardest robotic problems are DARPA Robotics Challenge [7], Amazon Bin Picking Challenge [8], and Mohammed Bin Zayed Robotics Challenge (MBZIRC) [9].

MBZIRC is an international robotics challenge that first took place in 2017. The competition is recognized worldwide as the cutting-edge test for collaborative heterogeneous multi-robot systems. The 2023 edition is called the Grand Maritime Challenge. It is divided into two main phases: simulation and demonstration. In the simulation phase, all participating teams must implement their solutions in the Ignition Gazebo Simulator [10] with ROS 2 galactic. Teams are evaluated on how quickly and accurately they execute a sequence of given tasks. One of the tasks was to recognize and retrieve objects of interest from the target vessel to the unmanned surface vehicle (USV) in a large GNSS-denied area. The simulation testbed used to develop cooperation between the robotic manipulator (RM) and the unmanned aerial manipulator (UAM) to solve a task is shown in Fig. 1.

This paper presents the control approach we used to solve the task of retrieving a recognized object from the vessel to the USV using heterogeneous robot collaboration in the GNSS-denied environment. We also present the networked control scheme used to overcome challenges encountered during the object retrieval task.

The contributions of this paper are as follows:

- 1) *Remote position based visual servoing in a heterogeneous robotic team;*
- 2) *Study of the effect of message loss probability on the reliability of a networked intermittent control system.*

The paper is organized into four sections. Section II presents related work from which we differentiate. Section III presents system design, control structures, and robot models used for solving the object retrieval task. In Section IV we present simulation experiments for validation of the proposed methodology. Section V concludes the paper and presents future work.

II. RELATED WORK

In this section, we present related work for visual servoing and networked and cooperative control of the multi-robot system. Guenard et al. [11] developed an image-based visual servoing (IBVS) UAV system which is capable of stationary or quasi-stationary flight. IMU measurements coupled with image features are used to estimate linear velocity and gravitational inertial direction. For UAV control, a nonlinear backstepping controller is used. Dufek et al. [12] have shown how to use a UAV for visual pose estimation of a USV to assist in the recovery of drowning victims. They showed that it is possible to use visual pose estimation as an aid in search-and-rescue tasks where UAV and USV collaborate. Watanabe et al. [13] developed IBVS of the UAV. The control feedback measurements are obtained from a stationary camera that observes the helicopter. The system shows that it is possible to control the UAV without any sensing capabilities if we can measure its behavior from outside. We use outside measurements for position-based visual servoing (PBVS) of the UAM. Wynn and McLain [6] presented a control system for the precision shipboard landing of the multirotor. They used visual servoing for aligning the multirotor with the landing target on the vessel. IBVS and a feed-forward term estimated by the Kalman filter were used to drive the multirotor toward the landing target. The collaborative system consisting of a robotic manipulator and a UAM presented herein can be considered a Networked Control System (NCS). In general, NCS is a control system where different parts are spatially distributed and connected with a band-limited lossy communication network. In [14], authors have shown that the tracking error in an NCS depends on its internal characteristics such as non-minimum phase zero, time delay, and unstable poles, but more importantly, on packet loss and bandwidth limitation as well. Schwung et al. [15] proposed a cooperative control method for autonomous objects that are connected by an unreliable communication network. The system fulfills the following control objectives: planning the trajectory between the objects, monitoring the distance between UAVs, following the planned trajectory, and compensating for external disturbances. The paper concludes that the simulation study proves the method is able to achieve all control aims despite the occurrence of time delays and packet losses. In [16] authors investigate multi-agent control in degraded communication environments. Authors found Maximally Allowable

Transmission Intervals (MATIs) between robots that satisfy certain performance for external disturbance rejection and validated it experimentally. Acciani et al. [17] explored the effects of packet loss on cooperative adaptive cruise control. The authors have concluded that without the observer, the stability of the system deteriorates quickly as the number of dropped messages increases.

One of the most common middlewares for implementing NCS in the robotics community is ROS [18]. In [19], the motivation and design of ROS 2 are presented. Compared to ROS, ROS 2 addresses some of the fundamental design challenges that have kept ROS from becoming the de facto industry standard for robotics. As ROS Noetic end of life is May 2025, it is in the best interest of the robotics community to begin migrating code and start development for ROS 2.

III. PRELIMINARIES

The heterogeneous system considered in this work is comprised of several different unmanned systems: an unmanned surface vehicle (USV), a robotic manipulator (RM), and an unmanned aerial manipulator (UAM). The RM is mounted on the USV to retrieve large objects. RM was used as a visual observer during the object retrieval with the UAM. The RM used in the simulation is the Schilling Orion 7P¹. The robotic arm has a mounted in-hand camera that is used to track the UAM during the object lifting procedure. UAM consists of a suction-based gripping mechanism mounted on a standard quadrotor UAV. Simulation is implemented in the Ignition Gazebo environment with a custom world, robot models, and plugins that simulate a coastal environment with hydrodynamics and wind. The control of the USV is beyond the scope of this paper. We assume that the USV has already successfully docked near the vessel of interest. UAM is controlled with velocity commands. RM is controlled by sending joint position commands.

A. UAV model

In the scope of the MBZIRC challenge, the UAM model was provided without modification as presented in this section. The controller for the UAM is implemented using a base RotoRS Lee Velocity Controller implementation from [20]. This is in turn an approximate implementation of the Lee Velocity Controller presented in [21]. The controller and the quadrotor UAM parameters are presented in table I.

TABLE I: Parameters used for quadrotor modeling in the simulation.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
motor constant c_t	$2.52 * 10^{-5}$	body mass	1.5 kg
attitude gain k_{ax}	10	rotor mass	0.005 kg
attitude gain k_{ay}	10	gripper mass	1 kg
attitude gain k_{az}	0.15	\ddot{x}_x	$< 1 \text{ m/s}^2$
velocity gain k_v	2.7	\ddot{x}_y	$< 1 \text{ m/s}^2$
attitude rate gain k_{Ω_x}	0.4	\ddot{x}_z	$< 2 \text{ m/s}^2$
attitude rate gain k_{Ω_y}	0.52	\dot{x}	$< 3 \text{ m/s}$
attitude rate gain k_{Ω_z}	0.18	Ω	$< 3 \text{ rad/s}$

¹<https://www.innova.no/wp-content/uploads/2015/04/ORION-7P-Datasheet-1.pdf>

The inertia matrix for the body of the UAV is approximated as

$$I_u = \text{diag}([0.025 \quad 0.009 \quad 0.033]), \quad (1)$$

where diag represents the diagonal matrix. The inertia matrix for the suction gripper that is modeled as a cylinder is

$$I_g = \text{diag}([0.00166 \quad 0.00166 \quad 0.00166]). \quad (2)$$

The inertia matrix of the whole system (UAV and suction gripper) is the sum of the inertia matrix of the UAV body and the inertia matrix of the gripper, transformed into the coordinate frame of the UAV body using the parallel axis theorem. The inertia matrix of the whole system without the payload is

$$I = \text{diag}([0.041895 \quad 0.025895 \quad 0.049895]). \quad (3)$$

The inertia and the mass of the rotors are omitted due to the negligible effect on the whole system. We control the UAM in the simulation using linear and angular velocity commands.

Table II shows that adding a gripper changes system performance. Any additional load can destabilize the system. Pounds et al. have shown that PID control is sufficient to reject dynamic load disturbances caused by the load mass and changing mass-inertia parameters [22].

TABLE II: Characteristics of velocity transfer functions for the UAV with and without the gripper.

Transfer function	Natural frequency (ω_n)	Damping factor (ζ)	Open loop gain	Location of the zero
$G_{x,UAV}(s)$	2.377	0.912	0.932	80.489
$G_{x,gripper}(s)$	1.151	1.361	0.922	-3.337
$G_{y,UAV}(s)$	2.191	0.775	0.889	19.649
$G_{y,gripper}(s)$	1.444	1.476	0.884	-8.053
$G_{z,UAV}(s)$	2.076	0.871	0.929	-4.537
$G_{z,gripper}(s)$	0.831	1.108	0.962	-2.665

B. Perception

We used two cameras for active control purposes. One camera is in-hand RGBD camera located on the Schilling Orion 7P, as shown and explained later in the paper. The second camera is an RGBD camera located under the UAM with the z axis of the camera frame pointing down. Both cameras are identical and their intrinsic matrix is

$$K_a = \begin{bmatrix} 554.5 & 1 & 320.5 \\ 0 & 554.5 & 240.5 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

The resolution of the camera is 640x480 and depth information is available for distances that range from 0.1 m to 10 m. For detecting the object of interest (small blue case) we use HSV filtering and centroid detection as shown in Fig. 2.

Besides RGB information, we use depth (Fig 3) for detecting and estimating UAM position and linear velocity during flight.

Fig. 2: Snapshot from the UAM camera stream during object approach (right), and HSV filtered image with a detected centroid (left).

Fig. 3: Image acquired with depth sensor on RM during UAV approaching vessel. Left image shows $t(k-1)$, right image shows $t(k)$.

C. Communication model

The communication plugin provided in the simulation enables two robots to exchange messages if they are within communication range d_{max} . Messages are serialized and sent over a single hop. The communication model imposes two limitations:

- 1) Each message is dropped with some probability P_{drop} ,
- 2) There is a maximum data rate allowed among robots communicating over the same network segment (e.g.: 1 Gbps).

Due to the task design, robots were always within communication range and we evaluated system performance at different constant drop rates.

D. State machines

The state machine for the UAM during the object transport task consists of the following states.

- *PREGRASP* → Send UAM in the negative z -direction (triggered when we are at a certain height above the object of interest).
- *GRASP* → Activate suction gripper when contact has been detected.
- *LIFT* → Lift UAM by a certain offset along global z axis.
- *GOTODROP* → Navigate UAM to the object drop point (USV base).
- *DROP* → Drop the object.
- *IDLE* → Hover in place.

RM has a simple state machine that consists of two states: *IDLE* and *FOLLOW_UAV*. When RM is in the *IDLE* state, it just retains its current configuration. When RM is in the *FOLLOW_UAV* state, it uses simple control to follow detected UAM with the end-effector camera.

E. UAM visual-based control

The predefined Lee controller was not good enough in terms of tracking the commanded velocities in cases where the object was grasped with a misaligned center of mass (CoM). The object was frequently grabbed with a misaligned CoM due to ship motion. In order to retrieve the grasped object, we needed to develop a cascaded control structure that would allow reliable tracking of references. The outer loop with the P controller² is used to track the position command and generate velocity references. The inner loop of the PI controller is used to improve the tracking of the velocity command when the object is grasped with misaligned CoM. The cascaded control structure is shown in Fig. 4. The

Fig. 4: Cascaded control structure used for visual-based UAM control in GNSS denied environment. Yellow arrows represent coordinate system transformations used for PBVS.

frequency of the controller is 40 Hz. Controller parameters are presented in Table III. Controllers were tuned for the UAM without load.

TABLE III: Parameters for the cascaded UAM control structure.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
PID1 - P	0.1	PID1 - limit	0.5 m/s
PID1 - I	0.0	PID1 - windup	0.0
PID2 - P	1.0	PID2 - limit	3 m/s
PID2 - I	3.0	PID2 - windup	1.0

Since we are working in an environment where GNSS is not available, we use the RM camera to measure UAM position and velocity. In this approach, we assume that the sky above the ship is open space. This assumption is valid since the mission is conducted in open waters, but it could also be applied to other scenarios if the surroundings are known. Due to this fact, it is easy to segment the UAM from the point cloud instead of an image. The position measurements are used for the PBVS of the UAM. We know the transformation between the RM camera and the USV base (drop-off point). Using matrix multiplication, we can determine the approximate position of the UAM in the USV base. Since the onboard controller accepts the commands in

the UAM base frame, we navigate the UAM to the USV position in the UAM frame.

Using homogeneous transformation matrices, we can calculate the estimated position of the UAM in the USV frame as

$$\mathbf{T}_u^l = \mathbf{T}_c^l \mathbf{T}_u^c. \quad (5)$$

With the following matrix inversion, we can determine the pose of the USV in the UAM frame:

$$\mathbf{T}_l^u = (\mathbf{T}_u^l)^{-1}. \quad (6)$$

The pose of the USV in the UAM frame is used as a position measurement for the control structure of the UAM. Such a system is heavily dependent on the camera sensing from the RM so it is crucial that the UAM remains in the camera FOV during object transportation.

Position reference sent to UAM is defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{p}_{ref} = [0.0 \ 0.0 \ z]. \quad (7)$$

We use such a defined position reference because we want to position the UAV directly above the USV drop-off point. \mathbf{p}_{meas} is the USV position estimate obtained from the RM camera measurements and the aforementioned transformation chain. Besides \mathbf{p}_{meas} we estimate the velocity \mathbf{v}_{est} as follows:

$$\mathbf{v}_{est} = (\mathbf{p}_{meas}[k] - \mathbf{p}_{meas}[k-1])\Delta t. \quad (8)$$

Sampling time Δt is the time difference between two position measurements k and $k-1$. We use a first-order filter to prevent unwanted velocity measurement spikes caused by small Δt :

$$\mathbf{v}[k] = \alpha \mathbf{v}_{est}[k] + (1 - \alpha)\mathbf{v}[k-1], \quad (9)$$

where the filter strength is set to $\alpha = 0.9$.

F. Assumptions

To simplify the control of the UAM in the GNSS-denied environment, we have made some assumptions that are appropriate for the problem at hand:

- 1) The heading (i.e., yaw angle) of the UAM remains at 0.0, controlled by the on-board P controller and measurements from IMU. In reality, this is acceptable since the compass rarely drifts significantly during short mission.
- 2) The drop-off point remains at constant height offset with respect to the z axis of the USV base.
- 3) The simulated camera was an accurate depth camera. For the algorithm to work in the real world, we would need to use a 3D lidar instead of the depth camera.
- 4) During object transport, we assume that the UAM is visible to the RM camera. In practice, we would need to set up a search state in the RM controller to ensure that the UAM is within the FOV before executing the mission.

²<https://gitlab.com/Juulbl/ros2-pid/>

IV. SIMULATION EXPERIMENTS

We conducted several simulation experiments to test the effect of message drop probability on the reliability of the UAM network control for the successful execution of the object retrieval task. We evaluated the system when the object was grasped in a such way that the load CoM is aligned with the CoM of the UAM, and when the CoM of the load was misaligned. We performed 10 runs for each of the message drop probabilities (0.1, 0.5, 0.75, 0.8, 0.85, 0.9, 0.95, 0.99) and for both load CoM alignments (aligned, misaligned).³ In Fig. 5 we show position references and measurements with different message drop probabilities. The legend shows $\langle \text{drop rate probability} \rangle \langle \text{suffix} \rangle$, where the suffixes m and c stand for measurement and command, respectively.

Fig. 5: Comparison of the position references and measurements when the object is grasped at the CoM for different message drop probabilities.

From observing Fig. 5 and Fig. 6, one might conclude that increasing the message drop probability increases task duration, but conducting several experiments revealed otherwise. Increasing message drop probability to a certain value decreases task duration. The inflection point for the experiment duration depends on the load CoM alignment. For the load with aligned CoM, the experiment duration decreases until P_{drop} equals 0.8, as shown in the right y axis of Fig. 7. For the misaligned load CoM, the experiment duration is decreased until P_{drop} equals 0.5. We compared the message drop probability with the success rate of the task for two different load alignments as shown on the left y axis of Fig. 7. Measurements for the P_{drop} 0.99 were omitted because the success rate for such drop probability is 0.

The probability of the message drop in a certain range facilitates faster task execution. The reason for that can be twofold. The first is that the frequency of the received feedback measurements is lower compared to the frequency of the controller. A mismatch between these frequencies

³Video of the experiments. Code developed for the experiments.

Fig. 6: Comparison of the position references and measurements when the object is grasped outside of the CoM for different message drop probabilities.

Fig. 7: Blue color shows experiment success rate and red color shows average experiment duration time of the successful experiments.

results in aggressive control. The second reason is that the controller uses only the last received measurement to generate the command. Since the measurements remain the same, the inner loop PI controller is bound to correct the existing steady-state error until the new measurement arrives. This behavior is shown in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9, which show $\mathbf{v}_{cmd} - \mathbf{v}_{meas}$ for the different message drop probabilities and different load CoM alignments. This behavior is especially observed for the higher message drop probability.

We can conclude that the load CoM alignment significantly affects system reliability, especially when there is a high probability of the message drop as shown in Fig. 7.

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, we implemented the cascaded PID structure and managed to successfully perform the task of object retrieval with intermittent visual servo control. The task was executed with a collaborative heterogeneous team of robots, exchanging information in real-time during mission execution. We verified the reliable operation of the developed control structure with multiple experiments in the simulation environment. We tested the robustness of the system with different configurations of the lossy network parameters

Fig. 8: Comparison of the velocity error when the object is grasped at CoM for different message drop probabilities.

Fig. 9: Comparison of the velocity error when the object is grasped with misaligned CoM for different message drop probabilities.

P_{drop} for the different load CoM alignments. We conclude that such a simple control system shows promising results, especially for environments where GNSS is not available. Further work would include increasing system reliability by using IMU measurements and a Kalman filter for position dead reckoning in case UAM is not in the RM camera FOV. Testing and validation of such a system on real hardware could also be beneficial to the community.

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